

SUSTAINABLE MORTARS FOR FACADES RESTORATION

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Abstract

Mortars are used in restoration works in many ways. In this work we consider two very common uses: to reconstruct lost part of ashlars or sculptures or as facade renders. Such mortars should satisfy several criteria such as the chemical and physico-mechanical compatibility with original components of the masonry but also aesthetics criteria as colour compatibility with stones or with former renders. Nowadays another criterion must be considered: their environmental footprint. In this work we present two studies about the sustainable use of mortars: a) the use of recycled sands from ancient renders for the application of new renders in the same façade and b) the estimation of mortars formulations' environmental impacts by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

For the use of recycled sands, we recovered then from deconstruction mortars that were crushed. The recovered sand was characterized and used for the formulation of new mortars with hydraulic lime. Washing methods with water and acid washing solutions have been tested in order to obtain sands free of debris and lime agglomerates. Citric acid was chosen because of its facility to be used in real restoration works. Sands washed only with water show some remaining parts of lime on the grain surfaces whereas washing the grains with citric acid solution (2 %) produces excellent results. Physical and mechanical properties of the new formulated mortars have been measured and show mechanical properties similar to mortars made using commercial sand.

For the LCA study twelve mortars were formulated using air lime, hydraulic lime or Portland cement as binders. LCA was used to quantify the potential environmental impacts on the categories of global warming potential, abiotic resources depletion potential-fossil fuels, acidification potential, and the photochemical oxidants creation potential of mortars. Hydraulic lime binders perform better in all evaluated environmental impacts. The critical hot spots are the transport model assumptions, and the fuel used for the binder production; using natural gas instead of mineral coke may reduce the global warming potential between 14 and 22 %, depending on the type of binder.

Keywords: Restoration mortars, sustainability, life cycle assessment, reuse.

1. Introduction

The built environment is responsible for a significant consumption of energy and resources, in particular 50% of all the natural extracted material. Nowadays the respect for the environment and the safeguarding of natural resources obliges many decision-makers and companies to seriously encourage the recovery of waste and the use of recycled materials.

Projects to renovate the built heritage for current and future generations present strong real estate and cultural stakes but, like construction projects, raise a problem of scarcity of natural sands. The old mortars and plasters were made, for most of them, with "natural" sands, generally alluvium and river sands, available near the site. These sources of sand are no longer available or have become rare.

In addition to this dual environmental and economic aspect, the use of sands other than the original ones has consequences on the appearance of the new plasters applied during the renovation, which often requires the use of additives and dyes. All these observations therefore raise the problem of how to renovate an old building, i.e. repair its alteration caused by time or human activity, without distorting its identity and the environment. In this sense, reusing materials from the renovation process is the panacea to maintain authenticity, compatibility, durability and preserve mother nature.

Studies conducted in France and other parts of the world have shown that recycled sand can be used as a single or partial aggregate in the formulation of concretes and mortars. Our study is part of the policy of valorisation of old plaster sands

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by their use in the formulation of new mortars. The study contributes to an innovation of systems for the renovation of built heritage by taking into account the socio-economic, technical, climatic, cultural and aesthetic contexts.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology has been formally developed since the late seventies (Guinée *et al.*, 2011) and intended to predict the potential impacts of products and processes on the environment, from resource extraction to product end-of-life (Ioannidou *et al.*, 2014). The LCA methodology has been standardized by the International Standardization Organization (ISO) in the ISO 14,040 series.

Lime binders, extensively used in cultural heritage building for many well-known reasons, are also interesting from the carbon capture perspective as air lime binders recapture the CO₂ released during the lime calcination. The reactions taking place in the lime cycle are: calcination, with the formation of calcium oxide; hydration of CaO to portlandite (Ca(OH)₂), and lime carbonation, which occurs naturally after the binder has been applied (Pavlik 2012). CO₂ recapture of hydraulic lime is lower than in aerial lime.

2. Environmental impact of the use of recycled sands

In a previous work (Diaz *et al.*, 2022) we have estimated the environmental impact of lime mortars produced by the employed materials, the fabrication and operational phases and their final disposal. We have reported several environmental impact categories, such as global warming potential (GWP), acidification potential (AP), abiotic resources depletion potential-fossil fuels (ADP-FF) and the photochemical oxidants creation potential (POCP). Diaz *et al.* (2022) described how these results were obtained. In the actual paper we use some data from this previous work in order to estimate the environmental interest of using recycled renders and mortars in general.

Figure 1 shows a compilation of the Diaz *et al.* (2022) results for the environmental impacts of different factors of the life cycle of mortars: employed materials, fabrication processes, use (operational) period and end of life. According to Life cycle assessment results, sand production has a very low contribution to the total environmental impacts, but we must consider other factors affecting the total impact. Reemploying renders as aggregates for new renders will contribute to reduce the materials transport of 70% (percentage of sand in the mortars) because ancient renders will be retreated onsite. In the Transport, Mixing and Preparation (TMP) parameter, we estimate that transport is the most important factor, we estimate its contribution as 75% of the total TMP. So, the use of recycled sands will contribute to reduce the TMP of 50% (~70%*75%). We can also consider that reuse will reduce the disposal phase of 60% as the mortars as constituted of 70% of aggregates and that in the recycling phase, we can reuse 80% of the original mortars. During the grinding procedure we have lost only 5% of the original weight. Around 10% in weight of the obtained particles are bigger than 2.25 mm, as will be presented in section 3.1, and they will not be employed in the fabrication of new mortars. Because these results have been obtained in “laboratory” conditions we have applied a security factor of x2 as in real condition many different operational factors can reduce the productivity ratio. We did not consider the “operation” phase that corresponds to the CO₂ absorption during carbonatation of lime. Applying these estimations to the data in Figure 1 we can conclude that the reuse of mortars as aggregates can contribute to reduce the photochemical oxidants creation potential of 30%; the acidification potential of the abiotic resource’s depletion potential-fossil fuels of 40%; the 40% and the global warming potential of 40%

Figure 1: Hydraulic lime mortars environmental impact.

3. Recycled sand from building renders

3.1 Materials

About 150 kg of renders coming from a 19th façade in Baugé-en-Anjou (49) have been collected. Around 1/3 of these renders come from a height of less than 2 m from the ground and the others from heights higher than 2m. Original material can be observed in Figure 2. The original material has been grinded in CONTROLAB jaw crusher, tuned to obtain the finest fragments, 2 mm. The grinding procedure has been done twice as the size of some particles were much higher than the announced 2 mm. The obtained particles are in the fraction 0/5. In the grinding process we lost approximately 2.5% of the original material.

Figure 2: Original deconstruction material, macroscopic samples, optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy.

In order to reemploy these materials, we have tested different treatments. The first one consists in washing the particles in water to eliminate the fine particles. Particles are placed in a container with water and mixed to allow fine particles to be in suspension in the water. Turbid water was eliminated. This procedure was performed several times until the water was almost clear. To eliminate as much as possible lime deposits, we tested washing with different acids: hydrochloric, citric and nitric. Citric acid gave the best results and is less harmful for the environment. Three different concentrations, 1%, 1.5% and 2% in weight, and two immersion duration, 1 day and 3 days, were tested. The best results have been obtained with 2% solution and 3 days immersion. A commercial sand from a materials store recommended for mortars preparation was studied for comparison. The difference between the original crushed material and the water washed one is shown in Figure 3. Particles have been distributed by granulometric fractions.

Figure 3: Materials employed in the fabrication of mortars.

3.1.1 Material characterization

Crushed material has been characterized at the original state, after water washing and after acid washing. The first test was the estimation of the salt content by the determination of the electrical conductivity of the solution resulting from the immersion of crushed materials in demineralised water. Keeping constant the weight of the sample and the amount of water for all the tests we determined that the electrical conductivity of solutions from original crushed material is 15 times higher than the solution of commercial sands for mortars coming from higher than 2m and 30 for mortars from under 2m. For the crushed materials washed with water, the electrical conductivity is around 3 times that of commercial sands for samples higher than 2m and 4% for samples under 2m. Similar results were obtained for samples washed with acids: for citric and hydrochloric acid, 2 times over 2m and 2.5 times under 2m. The obtained result confirmed what was expected, renders under 2m have a higher salt concentration than those located higher than 2m. We can also conclude that the washing procedure is quite efficient in the desalination as the conductivity has been reduced by 6 (+2m) and 7.5 (-2m) for water and 8.5 (+2m) and 11.5 (-2m) for acids.

Original mortars and crushed materials have been observed under optical and scanning electron microscopy (Figure 1 & 3). We can observe the grain size heterogeneity and the presence of dark minerals. The lime present on the grains on original materials is clearly observable.

The original crushed material and the washed ones have been sieved to characterise the granulometry of the obtained products. The granulometry after water and acid washing have been also measured. In Figure 4 we can observe the granulometric distribution of 500g of particles of grinded, grinded and washed (water and citric acid) materials. The main grain size is the same for all the materials but for the grinded one, the amount of fine materials is higher than for the washed one. The fraction over 2.25 mm is between 20 and 25% for all the samples. This fraction is made of original big grains but also of mortar fragment that have not been grinded.

Figure 4: Granulometry of the obtained sands.

Considering the water washing materials we can observe that under 300 μ m the grains are mainly formed of original grains with a low amount of lime. Between 600 μ m and 1 mm, grains are still single grains but with a higher amount of remaining lime. Between 1mm and 2 mm single grains and particles composed of several grains, fragments of the original mortar, are present. Most of the particles higher than 2mm are composite particles even if big grains of single minerals can be observed. These observations lead us to consider that the original sand was composed of quartz grains with some dark minerals and that the grain size was between 0 and 2 mm.

For each fraction we have also measured the grains density with a water pycnometer. If we compare the results for grinded particles, water and citric acid washed particles, the fraction of more than 600 μ m presents a slight increase of the density; particles between 500 μ m and 1 mm: no change from grinded to water (2.6) and increase with citric washing 2.67. For particles between 1 and 2 mm: from 2.48 (grinded) to 2.6 (water washing) and 2.64 (citric acid washing). For particles between 2 and 4 mm the density changes from 2.49 for the grinded particles, to 2.56 for water washed and 2.62 for acid citric washed. We can deduce that washing, especially with acid, dissolved remaining lime of particles.

Figure 5: Water vapor absorption at 90% relative humidity and 25°C for the obtained sands.

This observation has been confirmed by data from water vapour absorption (Figure 5). For particles under 600µm water vapour absorption decreases with the size due to the specific surface but over 600µm it increases with size. We can explain this difference because bigger particles are, in most of the cases, mortar fractions with small aggregates and lime. For particles under 600µm water vapour absorption is higher in not washed particles (grinded) than water and acid citric washed particles. Differences between the two kinds of washing are not very high.

3.2 Formulation of recycled mortars

Two kinds of mortars have been formulated in order to test the quality of the recycled samples. In a first set of mortars, sands resulting from the citric acid washing and only two granulometries (from 250µm to 500µm and from 500µm to 1mm) have been formulated. In a second set of mortars, we employed sand washed with water and with size less than 2.25mm. The choice of both sets has been done in order to compare the influence of remaining lime in the properties of mortars. In the first case we employed the cleanest fraction of the more effective cleaning method, excluding the finest grains. In the second one we decided to use the simplest and cheaper method. In both cases the employed lime was hydraulic lime NHL 3.5 from Saint Astier company and the formulation in percent was 30% wt. of NHL and 70% wt. of sand. The amount of water was selected to keep the same consistency of the paste.

For sands obtained by water and citric acid washing, we decided to compare the effect of grain size. For this reason, samples with 3 granulometries have been employed: from 250µm to 500µm (called 500µm sand), from 500µm to 1mm (called 1mm sand) and a mixture of both (55% of 1mm and 45% of 500µm).

For the second set of samples, we compared the several properties of mortars formulated with recycled sands and mortars obtained with a commercial sand of approximately the same mineralogical composition and size than the original mortars aggregates, excluding particles bigger than 2.25mm. In Figure 6 we can observe the original, sand-recycled and commercial sand mortars.

Figure 6: Left, original mortar; centre, mortar formulated with water washed sand and right, mortar formulated with a commercial sand.

The mechanical properties of mortars have been determined at different curation times for both sets, so the comparison can only be done between samples of the same set. For the first set the curation time was 28 days, for the second one, due to experimental constraints, the curation time was 3 months. The results of the uniaxial compression strength are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of mortars.

Specimen	Compression strength MPa
Set 1	
500 μ m mortar	0.8
1mm mortar	0.95
Mixture mortar	1.65
Set 2	
Recycled sand	1.8
Commercial sand	1.5

For the second set of mortars, we measured also their porosity as well as the vapor water absorption. Porosity of mortars with commercial sand is about 26%, and 21.5% for recycled-sand mortars. The vapor water absorption isotherms of the three kinds of mortars can be seen in Figure 7. We can observe that the original mortar (render) absorbs less water than the other and that it loses 80% of the water it has absorbed, while the formulated mortars lose only around 55%.

3.3 Interpretation of results

Concerning granulometry of obtained samples, the main differences are observed in the fractions under 300 μ m. The grinded sample, without any other treatment, presents a higher amount of fine fraction than the two others. Another small difference can be observed in the biggest fraction, under 2.25 mm, the grinded and water washed samples have a quite similar amount of this fraction that slightly decreases in the sands washed with citric acid. We can suppose that citric acid can dissolve lime of the composite samples and reduce their size.

The differences between grinded materials and washed ones can be observed in the optical microscopy. Grinded material presents a small amount of lime at the surface. In particles washed with water this layer of lime is less important, especially in particles smaller than 1mm. These results are consistent with the other measurements of grain density and vapour water absorption.

Figure 7: Water vapour absorption and desorption isotherms (25°C) for the 3 types of mortars: original one, formulated with washed recycled sands and formulated with commercial sand.

Mechanical properties strongly depend on the aggregate size distribution, as many previous studies have already demonstrated. In our case we can conclude that mortars with a larger grain size distribution show higher uniaxial compression strength, independently of the kind of sand.

4. Conclusions and perspectives

This preliminary study shows the use of recycled sands coming from original renders present properties comparable to mortar obtained with commercial sands. We can also conclude that mortars formulated with recycled sands are quite similar to the original ones at the microscopic and macroscopic scales. This study must be completed with data about the durability of these mortars. Real scale exposition tests have started but more time is needed to obtain representative results.

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